

GENERATIVE AI APPLICATIONS FOR RISK AND CRISIS MANAGEMENT: THE GOOD, THE BAD, AND THE UGLY

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Abstract: Generative Pre-Trained Transformers (GPT) have a potential to drastically improve our ability to extract actionable knowledge out of unstructured and semi structured data, by automatizing the processing of unstructured and semi structured data in a generic way. Potential for use of generative AI in risk and crisis management is enormous, and ranges from extraction of specific knowledge from large document sets over real time processing of texts, pictures and even video materials, to semi-automated timely responses to misinformation. Unfortunately, this high potential also comes with high risks, as generative AI systems often produce incomplete and misleading information, especially on topics they haven't been explicitly trained on and on the topics where the training data is already tainted by misinformation. In this paper, we present several application classes where generative AI could help improve environmental risk management and climate change action, (2) discuss the common sources of errors, legal and ethical challenges in such applications, and (3) propose a "safe" pathway towards gradual introduction of generative AI in applications with high societal impact.

Keywords: *risk and crisis management, Generative AI, knowledge management, knowledge extraction, misinformation.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Successful risk and crisis management critically depends on availability and quality of the knowledge of risk causes, mechanisms, expected impacts and impacts and side effects of possible actions. Often, the underlying information sources are written by humans for humans, unstructured or semi structured, and automatically processing them is difficult. In the preparation phase, the crisis managers are challenged by a huge and ever-growing body of data on risks, innovative solutions, experiences, and best practices. In early warning and response phases, important information is often shared by citizens on the social media and easily overseen or misinterpreted. Moreover, the recent cases of COVID 19 and the ongoing Climate Crisis clearly demonstrate the dangers of both intentional and unintentional misinformation that may be difficult to spot and even more difficult to effectively counter before causing a damage.

Generative Pre-Trained Transformers (GPT) (Devlin, 2018; OpenAI, 2023) have a potential to drastically improve our ability to extract actionable knowledge out of unstructured and semi structured data, by automatizing the processing of unstructured and semi structured data in a generic way. Potential for use of generative AI in risk and crisis management is enormous, and ranges from extraction of specific knowledge from large document sets over real time processing of texts, pictures and even video materials, to semi-automated timely responses to misinformation. Unfortunately, this high potential also comes with high risks, as generative AI

systems are prone to errors and omissions and likely to generate convincingly looking misinformation, especially on topics where such misinformation is abundant on the web (OpenAI, 2023).

In this paper, we will: (1) introduce the key elements of the Generative AI systems; (2) present several classes of applications from the environmental risk management and climate change space, where generative AI could be useful, (3) discuss the common sources of errors, legal and ethical challenges in such applications, and (4) propose a “safe” pathway towards gradual introduction of generative AI in applications with high societal impact.

2. KEY ELEMENTS OF GENERATIVE AI SYSTEMS

“Generative AI” is a type of AI applications that mimics human creativity and produces high-quality generated content that (seemingly) never existed before. They can generate various types of contents, including poems, essays, images, songs and videos, answers to questions, report summaries, diagrams, and the computer code. While the actual level of creativity of the generative AI models can be disputed, they can definitely do more than merely putting together bits and pieces of materials they were trained on – for better or for worse. This section introduces the underlying architectural model of generative AI systems and discusses the importance of the training data for such models.

2.1 Transformer: a reference model

In 2017, Vaswani et al. (Vasawani, 2017) proposed the canonical “Transformer encoder-decoder architecture” that inspired the neural network architectures used in BERT (Devlin, 2018), current OpenAI family of models (OpenAI, 2023), as well as open-source models such as Llama-2 (Touvron, 2023). This architecture is schematically shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Overview of the transformer encoder-decoder architecture. Inner layer connections are omitted from the diagram for simplicity.

The encoder (central part in Figure 1) maps an input sequence of symbol representations to a sequence of continuous representations. The decoder (right part in Figure 1) receives the

encoder output plus its own output at the previous time step to generate an output sequence. Both encoders and decoders consist of layers (vertical boxes in Figure 1). Each layer takes input data, does some inner processing, and pushes data to the next layer. Layers help build abstractions, where the left side deals with generalized representations (e.g., series of words), moving across layers to more specialized text construction on the right (e.g., formed sentences). The encoder's first layer is a multi-head self-attention mechanism, and the second one is a fully connected feed-forward layer. The decoder also uses multi-head attention over the output of the encoder stack. The self-attention mechanism computes representations of its inputs and outputs, establishing global dependencies between them. Self-attention has been used successfully in several tasks, including reading comprehension, text summarization, and question-answering.

The input knowledge base (left part in Figure 1) consists of several data sources. The network training procedure adjusts many network parameters (or weights), that are edges connecting neuron units from one layer to another. Parameters' values change dependent on the minimization of error estimates between the generated and expected outputs. The softmax layer normalizes the multi-class output probabilities. The model training is costly, requiring considerable computing power because of the size and consequently complexity of the artificial neural network. The weight parameters can surpass hundreds of billions in the GPT-3 and achieve an estimated trillion of parameters in GPT-4 (OpenAI, 2023).

The transformer-based model uses learned embeddings to convert input and output tokens (i.e., roughly words) to vectors of dimension d . Each word forming an input sequence is transformed into a d -dimensional embedding vector (input embeddings). Once the model is created (training phase), it can be integrated for deployment in real-world applications (e.g., chat systems). The model usage in most deployed applications only requires inferences, which is just one traversal across the neural network (left to right in Figure 2) to produce an output from one input. Model parameter weights are not normally updated during the inference phase.

2. A CASE FOR GENERATIVE AI IN RISK AND CRISIS MANAGEMENT

Probably the best-known generic application of GPTs today is the OpenAI's ChatGPT: an application that allows users to have a free "conversation" with the AI on any topic of interest to the user. This application has been so successful that it prompted a discussion on ChatGPT being just a step away from becoming a "general purpose thinking machine" (Williams, 2023). On the other side of the spectrum, it is important to keep in mind that GPT was initially designed as tool that can utilize pre-trained neural networks to continue a sentence. As the size of neural networks, and the size of the training set grew, these models started exhibiting emergent ability to seemingly "understand" the conversation and answer questions in a way that resembles human interaction, to analyse and summarise unstructured texts, to generate essays, write computer code, or even produce seemingly innovative multimedia materials (Wei, 2022).

Based on success of the ChatGPT, it is tempting to imagine an AI application for the crisis and disaster management that users can interact with in the real time, just as they would with a human expert. For example, the users could ask the tool to explain them which steps they could take to become more resilient to the climate change, or how to become energy autarch – from

choice of technology, over legal requirements funding and subvention opportunities, to choice of actual providers, costs, benefits and side effects of various actions. Current generation of the GPT models can indeed be used to develop this type of applications, albeit with some limitations that will be discussed in the next section.

Alternatively, the GPT technology could be used to pre-process the documents, tag them with pre-defined vocabularies, produce structured summaries by answering specific questions so that the system users can easily discover the information they are looking for, and even to produce illustrations for the works based on such summaries. This type of text processing is essential part of knowledge management and needs to be performed either by document owners (e.g. when uploading project reports to the funding agency website or before uploading inventory reports to the knowledge bases of public authorities) or by the knowledge curators that aim to make a large set of documents more useful for their respective end-users. Replacing the human experts by the AI in this process would undoubtedly be welcomed by both classes of users and allow the knowledge curators to process the documents in a fraction of time they need for this task today.

Beyond these two obvious classes of applications, generative AI could for example help the users to generate reports, up to and including the research papers and funding applications (Parrilla, 2023), and possibly also interact with real time geospatial data sources and model predictors to also answer the questions such as “What were the five largest natural catastrophes in Austria in the last year” or even “When will the flood reach my house and where should I evacuate to?”.

3. KNOWN ISSUES

The transformer model is not a knowledge base per se but a statistical model of a knowledge base. Unlike traditional deterministic retrieval systems for knowledge bases, the stochastic nature of LLMs will lead the tool to invent an answer based on statistics if it does not know the answer. State of the art GPT applications will therefore often produce the outputs (e.g. text, illustrations) that are very nicely written and seem compelling at a first glance but turn out to be incomplete and misleading when examined more closely. Several common types of AI errors and challenges are discussed in details hereafter, followed with the discussion of the societal dangers that could be induced by uncritical use of the generative AI outputs in the risk and crisis management domain. All the tests listed were performed between September and November 2023.

3.1 Incomplete answers

We recently undertook a foolproof test to interact with a set of LLM chat-based systems to understand factual data extraction (Havlik and Pias, 2023). Our tests were by no means exhaustive, but sufficient to illustrate that the LLMs are very prone to providing incomplete answers. For example, we formulated the following user prompt that gives a contextual statement followed by a question:

User prompt: Key performance indicators show performance achieved and help track the progress of an activity. Can you list all indicators mentioned in the latest IPCC AR6 reports?

OpenAI chat GPT3.5-turbo stated that IPCC AR6 reports are not in the training data sources used for the model training, a time window of up to September 2021. The answer demonstrates the importance of the model knowledge temporal context.

ChatClimate engine, which uses GPT4 models that were fine-tuned to IPCC AR6 report data (<https://www.chatclimate.ai/>) correctly listed essential climate variables, i.e., key indicators across atmospheric, oceanic, cryospheric, and biospheric domains, as described on page 26, Chapter 2 of the IPCC AR6 WG I report: The Physical Science Basis (Gulev, 2021). However, the response finished stating that this report “does not hold enough details” to answer the question, although a detailed list of indicators is available on the page 27 of the report.

Finally, the IPCC Chat system (<https://ipcc.chat/Chat>) stated that the IPCC AR6 reports do not contain any list of key performance indicators. The answers provided by ChatClimate and IPCC Chat clearly indicate that the issue of incomplete answers persists even if the underlying data is made available to the underlying GPT model.

3.2 Hallucinations and misattributions

Ziwei Ji et al. (Ziwei, 2023) define artificial hallucination in natural language processing as the “generated content that gives the impression of being fluent and natural despite being unfaithful and nonsensical”. It is hard to specify or verify the existence of such contexts due to the underlying probabilistic inventions of the model. Hallucinations for LLMs have been categorized into two types:

- Type 1: Intrinsic hallucinations - the generated output contradicts the source content. For example, suppose an abstractive summarization task outputs that the target value for an energy performance indicator should be below 5500 kWh. When carefully checked, this output contradicts the source document that reports a target value below 2700 kWh under the same indicator.
- Type 2: Extrinsic hallucinations - the output cannot be verified from the source content (i.e., the source can neither support nor contradict the output). For example, the system generates text not mentioned in the source, fabricating, or citing sources of unrelated content to support the generated statements.

To illustrate hallucinations, we replicated a prompt with two questions handled in a recent ChatGPT “human-machine interview” on climate change, published on the Climate Foresight website:

User prompt: Let’s test this approach by looking at a climate-related question together and then checking the sources you use to answer my question. Could you tell me the environmental impact of AI-generated language models and provide scientific references in the text and links to the sources mentioned?

This prompt was submitted to a GPT3.5-turbo model via the OpenAI ChatGPT interface (Havlik and Pias, 2023). The OpenAI ChatGPT satisfactorily indicated that the impact is related to energy used by graphics processing units (GPUs) but failed to provide estimates or measurements of the energy used. This is acceptable and fits well with the “knowledge” the model holds. The uneasy part comes next: hallucinations could be observed for most references

to source content. Only one of the references supports the energy-related claims in the output. Remaining four references appear real and correct, but upon inspection turn out to be either non-existent or to cover unrelated topics. This also illustrates the “lack of attribution problem”, whereby the generative AI cannot link the output answer to the documents used in the model training.

3. METHODS FOR IMPROVING THE GPT OUTPUTS

3.1 Importance of the training data

One of the key issues in development of the Large language models is the availability and quality of the training data. Datasets used in training large language models include web-crawled data, English Wikipedia, and publicly available books. The amount of influence each dataset has on the model training process varies. Figure 2 illustrates the datasets used to train the GPT-3 model (OpenAI, 2023), with web data being the most dominant.

Figure 2: Treemap of datasets used for training the GPT-3 model.

These datasets and their role in LLMs are:

- Common Crawl (Filtered) [training influence: 60%] This corpus contains raw web page data, metadata extracts, and text extracts collected over more than 13 years of web crawling. GPT-3 developers took a few data curation steps to improve the quality of the unfiltered or lightly filtered versions of Common Crawl. Curation steps included filtering based on similarity to a range of high-quality reference corpora and fuzzy deduplication to prevent word redundancy.
- WebText2 [training influence: 22%] Curated high-quality dataset, expanded from the WebText dataset, collected by scraping outbound links that received at least three karmas from users on the Reddit social media platform. Only web pages curated by humans have been used.
- Books1 and Books2 [training influence: 16%] These data sources are internet-based books corpora, containing a subset of public domain books.
- English Wikipedia [training influence: 3%] Wikipedia is a standard source of text for language modelling. The text is written in expository prose and spans many domains.

This dataset has received an increased training influence percentage to have a greater effect on the trained model.

The datasets in Figure 3 were used in training GPT-3 models. Other variants of this dataset have been created and made publicly available (Gao, 2020). Data curation becomes a crucial process that sets apart one dataset from another. The objective is to consistently minimize the impact of poor-quality data by carrying out editorial cleaning, eliminating duplicate data, and discarding low-quality data. Provenance schemes can also be applied to ensure that data transformations are appropriately tracked.

3.2 Beyond initial training

Unfortunately, the web is full of intentional and nonintentional errors and outdated information on topics of interest to risk and crisis management, such as the climate crisis or COVID-19 pandemics. Since web crawling data makes up for a very large part of the training, this (mis)information is inevitably incorporated in the training data. Figure 2 illustrates some of the common methods for improving the quality of the GPT outputs beyond this stage, grouped by “context type” and “by the direction of the information flow.”

Figure 2: Common mechanisms for improving the quality of AI outputs.

The direction of information flow, i.e., knowledge transfer is represented on the x-axis in Figure 2. In a one-way transfer, the user consumes information generated by the AI system. In a two-way transfer, they engage with the AI system to provide extended context. The context, i.e. situational world perspective of the model, is represented on the y-axis in the figure. An enlarged view of essential facts is created during initial computing-intensive model training. This context can be extended with domain-specific knowledge for a fraction of initial training efforts.

Most of the work on AI generative tools centres on the bottom-left quadrant in Figure 4. Developers train an LLM on extensive pre-trained data with limited involvement of users in the process. The context becomes the world facts "stored" as the adjusted weights of the model's neural network architecture. The context's breadth, depth, and time window determine its data scope. For instance, GPT-4 generally lacks knowledge of events after much of its pre-training data cut-off date in September 2021 and does not learn from its experience (OpenAI, 2023).

Original context can be extended by **fine-tuning the model**, that is, by using a relatively small set of trusted data to adjust the model weight parameters. The main limitations of fine-tuning are the high computational effort required for re-training the model parameters and the risk of confusing the original model with new knowledge, resulting in an overall lower quality of the generated outputs. One promising source of fine-tuning and validating the generative AIs for risk and crisis management domains is the information available on the fact-checking websites that manually check the credibility of influential information that claims to be scientifically grounded. For example, CLIMATE-FEVER has constructed a trusted evidence base for a set of claims on Climate Crisis that were found on the Internet, with a group of climate scientists manually classified every sentence as (i) supporting, (ii) refuting, or not giving enough information to validate the claim (Diggelmann, 2020).

Another approach for extending the model context is **retrieval-augmented LLM**, which augments the query with more focused contexts pulled on demand from relevant documents. Retrieval-augmented LLM approach has shown promising results not only in resolving the issue of providing the models with the recent data, but also in improving the accuracy achieved while reducing the model complexity. The Retrieval-Enhanced Transformer (RETRO) obtained comparable accuracy to the GPT-3 model on the Pile dataset (Ghao, 2020), despite using 25x fewer parameters (Borgeaud, 2021). Main issues related to of retrieval-augmented approach are the tendency of the LLMs to ignore the contextual data and produce results based on its training data and in the limited amounts of data that can be provided to the AI along with the questions asked.

Prompt engineering is another approach that improves the quality of the answers by fine-tuning the task prompt. In this approach, natural language instruction is used as part of a two-way interaction, and input-output examples serve as a contextual preamble before asking the model to perform the task for an unseen example (Zhou, 2022). Like retrieval-augmented LLM, prompt engineering does not require further training or updates to the model weight parameters. Finally, the **Reinforcement learning from human feedback (RLHF)** is a method that uses "humans in the loop" for tuning the language models. RLHF uses a limited amount of human feedback to train a preference model. When an output makes sense to the user, the rating is higher than incorrect, unethical, or nonsense outputs. In the next step, the preference model mimics humans and is used as a reward model in reinforcement training (Christiano, 2017). This method can be further improved by using the human feedback to train the "supervisor" model, which in turn controls the output of the trainee model and provides feedback in stead of the human experts.

4. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR GPT USE IN RISK AND CRISIS MANAGEMENT

In risk and crisis management, data sources can be characterised as (i) trustworthy, i.e., good faith data grounded on accurate facts and evidence, including reputable scientific publications and high-quality international reports, and (ii) misinformation data: false or inaccurate data that exposes the facts wrongly. Misinformation does not need to carry specific harmful intent but can still lead groups of people to be misinformed about facts related to the risks caused by e.g. climate change or pandemics and eventually take decisions that may be harmful for them and for the society at large.

Imagine a situation, where a trusted organization body (e.g., government, civil protection, responders) were to provide a publicly accessible GPT chat specialized in one domain today, similarly to the chat systems providing access to IPCC reports that were discussed in section 3.1. Due to underlying technological issues, such system would occasionally misinform the users, either through omission or by inventing the information that is inconsistent with reality (hallucinations). The results could be risky if these users decide to act upon the misinformation. In addition to personal or institutional losses caused by such decisions, this could negatively affect the trust in authorities, and raise the question of responsibility and liability. This is especially dangerous in the fields that are politically sensitive and where misinformation is already abundant, such as the recent COVID-19 pandemic or the ongoing climate crisis.

Methods for improving the quality of the outputs that are presented in section 3 can help to mitigate this issue, but not to completely eliminate it.

In conclusion, no GPT outputs should be indiscriminately trusted today, and this is unlikely to change in foreseeable future. Nevertheless, some GPT based applications will inevitably emerge, targeting the cases where the ability of these systems to rapidly and inexpensively process large amounts of unstructured data and create nice, structured summaries thereof outweigh the risks of users acting upon misinformation.

In the case of risk and crisis management, the most promising applications are currently the ones where GPT based tools are used by experts, which are willing and capable of double-checking the information, because this helps them to perform the work they are paid to do more efficiently – even with the added overhead of having to double-check the results provided by the tool.

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